

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the tenth regular issue of 2023. In this issue, various topical aspects of computer science are covered by 18 authors from 8 countries in 6 articles. As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for their highly valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, sustain the quality of our journal.

In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles or special issue proposals for our journal.

As we want to secure the financial support also for the years to come, we are looking for institutions and libraries to financially support our diamond open access journal as consortium members, who will then benefit from the research community, international visibility, and the opportunity to manage special issues and focused topics within the journal. Please think about the possibility of such financial participation by your institution, we would be very grateful for any kind of support.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 6 accepted articles: In a collaboration between researchers from Palestine and Jordan, Rasha R. Atallah, Ahmad Sami Al-Shamayleh, and Mohammed A. Awadallah look into the impact of plastic surgery on face recognition models and propose a model based on an artificial neural network with model-agnostic meta-learning (ANN-MAML) for plastic surgery face recognition which results in an accuracy of 90% in all evaluation experiments. In another research collaboration between colleagues from Tunisia and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Samar Bouazizi, Emna Benmohamed, and Hela Ltifi propose in their article an advanced approach to recognize human emotions by using electroencephalogram (EEG) signals and focus their analysis on two specific classes of emotion recognition: H/L Arousal and H/L Valence. Anderson Melo de Morais, Fernando Antonio Aires Lins, and Nelson Souto Rosa from Brazil report on their survey on integration of consensus mechanisms into IoT-based blockchains, analyzing eight dimensions that help understand existing proposals: ease of integration, scalability, latency, throughput, power consumption, configuration issues, integrated algorithms, and adversary tolerance. In the next article Aymane Ezzaim, Aziz Dahbi, Abdelfatteh Haidine, and Abdelhak Aqqal from Morocco carry out a systematic mapping of the literature on AI-based adaptive learning environments and approaches. They examine

93 articles published between 2000 and 2022 and discuss the findings, including the types of AI algorithms used, the objectives targeted by these systems as well as the factors related to adaptation. Sergio-Daniel Sanchez-Solar, Gustavo Rodriguez-Gomez, and Jose Martinez-Carranza from México present their research on the control of a spherical robot rolling over irregular surfaces, which is achieved by controlling two motors for longitudinal and lateral motion in this non-holonomic system, and showed improvements by tuning the controller's gains using stochastic signals for the longitudinal controller. Last but not least, Layse Santos Souza and Michel S. Soares from Brazil propose in their article the joint use of the SmartCitySysML with TCPN (Timed Coloured Petri Nets) to refine and formally model SysML diagrams that specify internal behavior, and then verify the developed model to prove behavioral properties of an urban traffic signal control system.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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